

CARE FOR PEOPLE WITH WOUNDS AND STOMAS: EXPERIENCE REPORT

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SUMMARY

Introduction: Wounds represent the loss of skin integrity (injury) due to external causes (trauma or surgery), or due to internal or endogenous causes, related to diseases that facilitate or cause the wound. They can be classified as simple, when the healing time and phases occur in an orderly manner and according to a predicted time for the type and extent of the injury, or complex, when they do not respond to adequate treatment according to the etiology (factor causal) by metabolic or physiological complications. This treatment must necessarily be provided by a qualified professional, providing humanized care to the person with such a problem. **Purpose:** To describe the importance of the proper use of coverings in the treatment of wounds by people with wounds and stomas. **Methodology:** This is a descriptive study, of the experience report type. **Result and Discussion:** The topic addressed was about wounds and the main coverings used, since the main aspects observed in a wound are: anatomical location, necrotic tissue, drainage, edges, size, depth and granulation tissue. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that the proper use of covers in the treatment of wounds and stomas is of paramount importance for improving the quality of life of these people. The professionals who carry out these guidelines need not only technical-scientific knowledge based on evidence to carry out care planning that is adequate for the reality of each patient, but also a holistic, empathetic and human view with them during their approaches.

Keywords: Coverages; Wounds; Treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Stomatherapy is a specialty that is exclusive to the area of nursing and is dedicated to the care of patients with a stoma. According to Gonçalves (2018) in Brazil, the number of nurses specializing in stomatherapy has been increasing surprisingly. Care requires training in order to promote quality of life for patients with stomas, skin lesions and with anal and/or urinary incontinence, acute and chronic wounds, fistulas and insertions of catheters and drains (OLIVEIRA et al, 2023).

Ostoma, ostomia, stoma or ostomy are words with the same meaning, derived from the group “osto” mouth and “tomia” opening. It aims to temporarily or permanently divert a segment of the intestinal route through the elimination of fecal content in a collection bag usually adhered to the abdomen (OLIVEIRA et al, 2023).

In addition, it should be emphasized that the specialty is complex, as it involves a multidisciplinary activity, the use of different technologies and the provision of care in its

biopsychosocial dimension, it is necessary to develop unique and special skills and competences to act safely and with excellence, thus guaranteeing , the quality of life of people assisted and promotion of self-care (COSTA *et al* , 2020).

The stoma therapist is responsible for assisting patients in preventive, therapeutic and rehabilitation aspects, always looking for the best alternatives, as the intention, in addition to cure, is to improve the patient's/client's quality of life. It holds techniques and skills capable of offering various treatments with advanced technologies in addition to education in diabetes and prevention of ulcerative wounds due to diabetes mellitus, treatment of diabetic foot lesions with a focus on the prevention of amputations (CHOTTI, 2021).

METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive study of the experience report type, which deals with the care of patients with a stoma.

The database used to extract the scientific articles that will compose the present work was the Google Scholar platform, whose inclusion criteria were: articles that address the subject in question, articles published between the years 2020 to 2022. Exclusion criteria were: duplicate articles, which do not address the subject in question, reviews, publications in congress annals.

The keywords used were extracted from the health descriptors database (DECS): Coverage, Wounds and Treatment, whose purpose is to pass on relevant information to the general population in a clear and concise way.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The current labor market is marked by numerous demands, such as professionals with a high standard of qualification, with autonomy to make decisions, who are able to quickly incorporate technologies, and take responsibility for providing answers to the problems of the most different production processes. . In this way, professionals need to be prepared and able to adapt to the new trends imposed by the world of work (COSTA *et al*, 2022).

In this context, it should be noted that there has been a change in the Brazilian epidemiological profile, with a significant increase in the number of people who require specific stomatherapy care, due to the increase in individuals or those with a high risk of illness, due to external diseases, highlighting urban and violence violence. transit and care in stomatherapy

are increasingly important. Thus, there is a significant number of individuals with chronic and watery wounds, caused by diabetes mellitus, systemic arterial hypertension, leprosy, vascular disease, cancer, among others (COSTA et al, 2022).

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that the proper use of dressings in the treatment of wounds and stomas is of paramount importance for improving the quality of life of these people. The professionals who carry out these guidelines need not only technical-scientific knowledge based on evidence to carry out care planning that is adequate for the reality of each patient, but also a holistic, empathetic and human view with them during their approaches.

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